

Mobile charcoal pile prototype for biochar production in situ

Introduction

A prototype of vertical mobile charcoal kiln has been developed on a farm scale, with quite small dimensions, whose work for the charcoal-making operations is such that only one worker's day is sufficient.

The transformation of chestnut cultivation residues into biochar and charcoal is a good practice from a phytosanitary point of view, and furthermore, this activity allows for increased profitability on a small company scale, mainly focused on forest owners. These products can be further valorised on the farm or sold to third parties, thus becoming an additional source of income from materials that would otherwise have to be disposed of. Other promising products are condensate liquids derived from the pyrolysis process.

The prototype is structured with a vertical development, outlining a type of mobile kiln called 'vertical kilns with discontinuous operation', capable of operating in direct and indirect carbonization process.

The input material can be in the form of wood with varying diameters and length reduced to approximately one metre, (direct or indirect system), but also chopped wood or other residues (indirect system), coming from the cultivation of the chestnut grove, but also supplied by other sources within the owner forest production, such as pruning residues of other fruit trees or residues of silvicultural operations. The product obtained therefore has characteristics, even if only dimensional ones, that are peculiar and therefore destined to be used in the production of chestnuts.

The carbonisation that can be carried out in this prototype is a slow process that takes place at a low to medium temperature (below 500 °C), and is the system that yields a higher yield in solid product (charcoal), compared to rapid and/or high temperature pyrolysis systems (Bridgwater, 2007), an element that should not be underestimated at farm level.

Lessons learned

Considering the excellent results and the current need of chestnut growers to diversify and increase income, the mobile charcoal kiln has proved to be a machine capable of responding to the needs of chestnut farms, and the versatility of the direct and indirect system process also makes it suitable for all those farms that have agro-forestry waste, such as prunings from olive groves and vineyards, making the project multi-purpose in creating economic and employment induced from elements previously considered waste and above all not exclusively linked to chestnut growing.

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Further information

<https://www.psingeca.it/it>

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